

The LIAISON project: Objectives and output

LIAISON project - Better Rural Innovation: Linking Actors, Instruments and Policies through Networks

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Overview

1. About LIAISON
2. LIAISON's multi-actor approach
3. Output of LIAISON

1) About LIAISON

- LIAISON was a Research and Innovation Action
- Type: Multi-actor project
- Partners: 17 diverse organisations from 14 EU Member States and CH, NO and UK
- Duration: May 2018 – April 2022
- Budget: approx. 5 million Euro
- Homepage: www.liaison2020.eu
- Twitter: @liaison2020, #liaison2020

Aims of LIAISON

Why do some partnerships have the ability to organise themselves, to capture new ideas, to nurture them and create something new?

The project aimed to

- Understand better what makes a successful partnership for innovation,
- Encourage more of these successful partnerships for innovation,
- Develop recommendations to those providing the enabling environment for the implementation of such co-innovation projects.

What are multi-actor projects?

- A mixed group of actors with complementary competences
- working together in a co-creative way from the beginning of a new idea until the dissemination of innovative results (‘interactive innovation’).
- Funded under
 - the European H2020/HEU programme (RIA, IA, CSA),
 - the Rural Development Plans (OG, networks), or
 - other funding of project consortia with mixed groups of actors (LEADER, private fund etc.)

Focus on the 'I' - Innovation

*Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (a concept promoted by the European Commission)

2) LIAISON's own multi-actor approach

- Macro-regional stakeholder groups: stakeholder mapping, selection/invitation, three workshop events, bilateral exchanges
- Project Advisory Group representing different types of stakeholders
- Shared responsibilities within WPs and tasks
- Ethics Committee looking after GDPR and Gender, but helping also with mediation
- One workpackage only on 'How we work together'

LIAISON
Optimising interactive innovation

Actors and stakeholders in LIAISON

- 17 Consortium partners
- 30 In-depth case studies from across Europe plus 2 international case studies - Living Labs Canada and CDAIS Africa
- ★ 15 Rural Innovation Ambassadors

Approach to `How we work together`

- Co-design workshop on communication and collaboration in the first months
 - Annual self-reflection on our co-innovation processes and the own participatory learning
 - Ensuring awareness of multi-actor challenges
 - Critical assessment of the cooperation e.g. the sharing of responsibilities or the degree of inclusiveness - efficiency versus participation
- ➔ Ongoing awareness raising and critical reflection about the challenges when being a leader or a participant in a multi-actor project

Overview

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2. LIAISON's multi-actor approach
3. Output of LIAISON for multi-actor management, training, monitoring and evaluation and the improvement of the enabling environment

Management of multi-actor projects (MAP)

- Two sets of macro-regional workshops (2018, 2021)
- Practice-oriented LIAISON conference (2021)
- Self-reflection workshops during project meetings
- Partners' engagement in many new EU multi-actor project proposals (H2020, HEU, ERASMUS+ etc.)
- All partners engage in nationally (co)funded MAP (OG, networks, LEADER, LIFE+, national funds etc.)
- Seven partners provide national innovation support

Training / learning from good examples

- Several reports and scientific papers from the light-touch review of 200 MA partnerships
- 30 European case study analyses, 2 international <https://liaison2020.eu/our-network/case-studies/>
- European Rural Innovation Contest `EURIC` with the selection of 15 LIAISON Ambassadors

25/11/22

Videos: 1 LIAISON Journey and 15 Ambassadors
<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC6EKMM7Gh4wkhfA98RK9AMg>

Learning from good practices

The screenshot displays a detailed case study page for the Operational Group 'Hanfanbauer Werra-Meißner'. It features a header with project details, a 'Highlights' section with key takeaways, and a 'Good Practices & Lessons Learned' section with multiple sub-points.

Highlights:

- A truly farmer-led project, supported by a diverse stakeholder network
- The lead partner's management capacities, connections and competences are indispensable for the project
- Conflict of interest: knowledge dissemination vs. defending a niche market

Good Practices & Lessons Learned:

- Interaction with the funding mechanism:** Farmers see the advantage of the 'Operational Group' funding scheme in that it supports projects independently of their success. This gives them to take risks in the innovation process.
- Interaction between the case study partners:** The lead partner is the agronomist and driving force in the group, whereas all partners are lesser unanimously at eye level.
- Interaction with external stakeholders:** The group is closely connected with several types of organisations, including agriculture service providers, supply and sale businesses and public authorities. However, the involvement of researchers in the group's network is missing so far.
- Interaction with the case study context:** Long-established and only partly third-party restrictions on hemp production in Germany have resulted in a mix of value chains for hemp products. This makes the project original, but also demanding.
- Contributions to societal challenges:** If the group succeeds in establishing hemp value chains in the hemp-growing region, this could encourage others to follow and thus help to introduce an accompanying business alternative to the local agriculture.

32 Posters of the in-depth case studies
<https://liaison2020.eu/our-network/case-studies/>

The screenshot shows the 'Interactive Innovation Tool Box' interface. It includes a search bar, a list of documents with filters for Language, Document Type, Country, and Thematic Field, and a table of available guides.

Interactive Innovation Tool Box

Our Interactive Innovation Tool Box aims to offer easy access to all of the practical materials we have produced in the LIAISON project for you - the users of our results.

If you would like to provide feedback on our homepage and LIAISON material, or you have any questions for our authors, please do not hesitate to **contact us**.

Use the filter or search functions to find what you are looking for.
By default only documents in English are shown.

Name	Type	Size	Download
LIAISON - Coming together: How to Guide	PDF	304 KB	Download
LIAISON - Good Planning: How to Guide	PDF	398 KB	Download
LIAISON - Healthy Partnerships: How to Guide	PDF	387 KB	Download
LIAISON - Connected Partnerships: How to Guide	PDF	329 KB	Download
LIAISON - Achieving Impact: How to Guide	PDF	403 KB	Download

5 How-to-Guides for practitioners in
BG, DE, EN, ES, FR, HU, IT, PL, RO!
<https://liaison2020.eu/your-material>

Monitoring and evaluation of MAP

- Co-design of qualitative self-assessment in numerous workshops with external project groups (2019-2021)
- Co-design of quantitative approaches with a sub-set of the groups from the case study work (2021)

Improving the enabling environment

- Analysis of mechanisms in support of innovation
- Discussion paper challenges innovation actors are facing and the related research and innovation needs
- Administrative and financing challenges
- Macro-regional workshops; LIAISON conference
- Engagement with international organisations
- Contributions to the EU's Standing Committee on Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation SCAR-AKIS
- Set of Policy Briefs

To conclude

- It's evident, lots of progress has been made with the implementation of the EIP-AGRI policy concept since 2013
- But we are realising that several improvements remain challenging such as
 - ensuring cooperation between the different partners needed and their active engagement from project preparation until dissemination,
 - different speeds of providing the enabling environment for the establishment of co-innovation projects in Europe's rural areas.

➔ LIAISON's work on the insights from practice show that it is important to think bigger and keep an eye on the complexity of interactive innovation and the related capacities of all actors involved.

Thank you!

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<https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLSwCCZQECphqki10TZxJZmqNK6jj2fLI4>

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www.liaison2020.eu